

Speaking is a key tool for development of learners productive skills

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Abstract

One of the most important factors in communicating with others is our nonverbal communication. We are aware and in control of the words that we speak, but often the nonverbal cues we send may go unnoticed. “We can reinforce, contradict, substitute, complement, or emphasize our verbal communication with non-verbal cues such as gestures, expressions and vocal inflection.” Nonverbal cues are so strong because they communicate to others on a subconscious level, causing individuals to regard nonverbal communication as “true” communication because it provides real cues and emotions. When verbal language and body language are congruent, this works to enhance the overall quality of the message and allow it to resonate with the individual receiving the message. On the opposite end of the spectrum, there can also be a sense of mistrust developed when body language does not match up to what is being verbalized. When there is a lack of congruence between verbal and nonverbal messages, this acts as a mental red flag to anybody receiving the message, and causes them to be on guard. Body language also works to display confidence and other desirable traits. In the case of a potential job opportunity, displaying confidence can be the driving factor in whether an employee gets hired or not. Likewise, as an employer, it is essential to let applicants know that you are confident in the company and work you do.

Key words: essential, productive, significant, obvious, clear, reality, feelings, withdrawal, conceptual, regarding, felicitations, organizational, data

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Отрывок

Одним из наиболее важных факторов в общении с другими людьми является наше невербальное общение. Мы осознаем и контролируем слова, которые говорим, но часто посылаемые нами невербальные сигналы

могут остаться незамеченными. «Мы можем усиливать, противоречить, заменять, дополнять или подчеркивать наше вербальное общение с помощью невербальных сигналов, таких как жесты, выражения и интонация голоса». Невербальные сигналы настолько сильны, потому что они сообщают другим людям на подсознательном уровне, заставляя людей рассматривать невербальное общение как «истинное» общение, поскольку оно дает реальные сигналы и эмоции. Когда вербальный язык и язык тела совпадают, это повышает общее качество сообщения и позволяет ему найти отклик у человека, получающего сообщение. На противоположном конце спектра также может возникнуть чувство недоверия, когда язык тела не соответствует тому, что произносится. Когда существует несоответствие между вербальными и невербальными сообщениями, это действует как мысленный красный флаг для любого, кто получает сообщение, и заставляет его быть настороже. Язык тела также помогает продемонстрировать уверенность и другие желательные качества. В случае потенциальной возможности трудоустройства проявление уверенности может стать решающим фактором в том, будет ли сотрудник принят на работу или нет. Аналогично, как работодателю важно дать соискателям понять, что вы уверены в компании и работе, которую выполняете.

Ключевые слова: существенный, продуктивный, значительный, очевидный, ясный, реальность, чувства, уход, концептуальный, относительно, поздравления, организационные, данные.

Speaking is a fundamental language skill. It is the primary way in which we communicate information. When we ask how well we can function in a second language, we ask the question “how well do you speak...?”, so it is the ability to speak well which best represents our proficiency in another language.

As teachers, however, we must be mindful that speaking involves more than simply using words to articulate what we are thinking, and there is more at play than simply asking students to say the words that they know.

1. Communicative competence

Being a ‘good speaker’ requires a range of skills beyond accurate grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation, though these are the basic building blocks that enable a message to be understood.

An effective communicator chooses the words they use, and the way in which they speak to different people in different situations, whether that is ordering a sandwich at a snack bar or giving a keynote speech at an academic event.

The skills involved in how we interact with others in different ways are called communicative competencies: teachable skills which frame the language used in interaction in different settings.

Speaking as a language skill involves these competencies much more than it requires accuracy of language, so when we talk about ‘teaching speaking’, we are talking about something different from grammar or vocabulary practice.

Speaking can be used to practice new language (as is common in question-answer tasks or role-plays held after specific language instruction, but this kind of activity may not teach the skill of speaking itself.

2. Teaching speaking as a set of competencies

Just as we can instruct, present and practice specific grammar features to students, the component competencies which make up speaking as a pure language skill can also be broken down and presented systematically.

Some useful language sub-skills which can be turned into practice activities are:

Avoiding repetition

Responding appropriately while listening

Turn-taking techniques

Politeness

Circumlocution (talking around unknown words using known language)

Extending ideas

Notice that none of these sub-skills make specific reference to grammar, vocabulary or pronunciation, though obviously these are necessary for students to communicate what they want to say.

In order to bring the focus onto these competencies, it is therefore advisable to lead speaking tasks on topics that are familiar to students, and using language that is within their ability. Taking the strain of new language out of speaking activities allows students to focus on the pure sub-skills listed above.

This is similar to the way in which native speakers are ‘trained’ for public speaking or assertiveness in social situations: as native speakers, they are comfortable with the structure of their own language, but want to develop other skills which go along with that.

3. Discourse and organisation of message

Many of these features of speaking fall into the category of discourse – the organisation and style of a message as it is delivered in different situations.

When teaching speaking in a given context, think about how people actually speak in that situation.

Find recordings of people interacting in restaurants, banks, or wherever your lesson will be set, and think about the functional steps of the interaction as it happens.

You will probably find that most interaction that you listen to is quite formulaic and predictable, so can be used as a structure for the dialogues that you present and

practice in class, only with the organisation and ordering of the speech as the focus of the class rather than the specific language used.

Taking an opposite approach, think of situations where the above list of competencies is common.

For example: we often use circumlocution when we are talking about complex, technical subjects, like when we describe a problem we are having with a gas cooker, car engine or plumbing; we may not know the exact name of the part which is not working, but we can still communicate it to a gas fitter, mechanic or plumber.

This is a useful life skill, and one which can be used to harness second-language speaking for language learners.

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